

**Research Data Management and Open Science
Policy and Guidelines
Institute of Political Science,
Leiden University**

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1) Introduction

This document defines the Research Data Management and Open Science policy of the Institute of Political Science, in line with national- and faculty-level requirements. At the national-level, the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) sets out a framework for Research Data Management and research integrity in line with the principles of Open Science, along with the Guideline for the Archiving of Academic Research for Faculties of Behavioural and Social Sciences in the Netherlands ([DSW, 2022](#)). Within this context, Leiden University ratified its Data Management Regulation in 2021, and the Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FSW) ratified its ‘2024 Research Data Management Policy and Protocol’ (henceforth, the ‘Faculty Protocol’) on 01-06-2024. This policy thus elaborates on the guidelines laid out for the institute in the Faculty Protocol, focusing on research data management (RDM), data preservation, and Open Access publishing.

This policy also builds on existing laws and guidelines within whose remit researchers at the institute of Political Science should operate. This includes the principle of ‘**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**’ which underpins Open Science practices and data sharing.

There are several mandatory elements of this policy: namely, Data Management Plans and Publication Packages. Open Access publishing is mandatory for all short form publications; peer-reviewed articles and book chapters in edited collections. Adherence to GDPR,¹ which concerns ethics and privacy, is also required by law. All other elements are **guidelines for best practice** and are clearly delineated as such. Each section begins by stating which research projects fall under each policy. Questions regarding this should be directed to the institute data steward.

The institute’s data steward is always available to answer any questions, or to assist in the implementation of the guidelines and recommendations of this policy. For a list of relevant RDM staff, see [Appendix A](#).

1.1) To which data this policy applies

In line with the Faculty Protocol, research data refers to any material (re)used to support a knowledge claim. This encompasses digital and non-digital data, generated from the beginning of the research project until its completion.

Examples include, but are not limited to:

- Data generated from an experiment/survey/interview. Data gathered from secondary sources, data generated while processing/analysing secondary data;
- Software, models, script or code generated for the purpose of the research project, or as a research output;
- Metadata;

¹ The General Data Protection Regulation (In Dutch: Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming, AVG). This governs the handling and processing of personally identifiable information; see [section 4](#).

- Other relevant supporting materials.

In accordance with the Faculty Protocol, this policy does not treat field notes/personal notes as research data. Researchers are entrusted with extracting the relevant data from these notes to be included in RDM practices.

1.2) To whom this policy applies

As per the faculty protocol, if a researcher intends to publish under a Leiden University affiliation, this policy applies to them. This includes guest researchers who will publish under the Leiden University affiliation. As per the Faculty Protocol, this policy applies to all persons conducting research under the responsibility of the Institute of Political Science at Leiden University. This includes all employees, all PhD candidates, guest researchers,² retired colleagues and any other guests or partners who carry out research at the Institute of Political Science.

The Faculty Protocol states that research conducted by Bachelor's and Master's students falls under the formal responsibility of their supervisors. In the Institute of Political Science, we operationalise this in the following way: Coursework carried out by Bachelor's and Master's students, including their theses, is generally excluded from this policy. This policy only applies to a Bachelor's or Master's thesis or paper in the event that a student prepares this for publication, for example in a peer-reviewed journal, under a Leiden University affiliation. In such instances, the supervisor is responsible for ensuring that the student is properly informed about these requirements so that the student is able to meet the requirements of this policy with the help of the data steward.³

This policy comes into effect from 1 September 2024. Thus, all research projects started after this point fall under this policy. Projects started before this date are not obligated to apply this policy retroactively.

² Guest researchers who are affiliated with another research institution and conduct their research under that institution's rules and regulations and do not intend to publish under the Leiden University affiliation, are exempted.

³ In these cases, it is acceptable to draw up a Data Management Protocol retroactively.

2) Data Management Plan Policy

Scope: The Data Management Plan Policy is **mandatory** for:

1. Research funded by grants, whereby RDM should be carried out according to the funder's requirements;⁴
2. Research that is intended to result in any type of scholarly output, for example articles in an academic journal, a book published with an academic publisher, a chapter in such a book, or a preprint posted on an academic preprint server.

For research that falls under point 2, there are two **exceptions** (that thus do not require a DMP):

- Article reviews and book reviews, as these are not considered original research as defined by the Faculty Protocol;
- Projects constituted by the reading of existing texts that can be identified and referenced in the publication, without creating any derivative data (e.g. coded text, classifications, etcetera).

A Data Management Plan (DMP) consists of a series of questions and answers relating to data management responsibility within research teams, types and nature of the data that are expected to be produced and (re)used within a project, and the conditions under which these data will be collected, stored, analysed, shared, and archived in the long-term. This is an organic document that should be updated with significant changes to its constitutive elements.

Leiden University has its own DMP template which is accepted by the majority of funders. For funded projects, we recommend either using the Leiden DMP template or the template of the funder when applicable.

2.1) Responsibilities for writing and reviewing the DMP

Writing the DMP is the responsibility of the research's principal investigator/lead researcher. When a project is a collaboration, the RDM strategy should be discussed and agreed upon collectively. This is especially important for collaborations that involve researchers from third parties, where it is crucial to make clear the relevant parties' responsibilities over the data. In the event that the principal investigator is based in an institution that does not necessitate a DMP, it is the responsibility of the Leiden-based researcher to produce this document.

In the case of an externally funded project, the DMP should be sent to the institute data steward for approval prior to the DMP's submission to the funder. For all other projects, the DMP must be sent to the data steward for review before data collection begins. Feedback will be provided by the data steward within one month of receipt; sooner when possible. An updated DMP should also be sent to the data steward after the research is completed. The data steward will archive this final version of the DMP in line with Faculty Protocol.

⁴ Please note that the exceptions listed in this box do not apply to funded research.

2.2) Personal Umbrella DMPs

An umbrella DMP is a data management plan that applies to multiple research projects. Within the Institute of Political Science, researchers can opt to write an individual umbrella DMP, which applies to all of their research that is not covered by a project-specific DMP. Writing a personal umbrella DMP prevents the need to produce a new DMP for each new research project.

To create this personal umbrella DMP, the Institute offers a flexible template that can combine various parts for different methods to create a DMP that suits an individual researcher ([Appendix B](#)). The data steward can provide advice on how to do so. The personal umbrella DMP needs to be adjusted when a new project significantly deviates from a researcher's standard practices.

Writing a personal umbrella DMP is not required, but if a researcher chooses not to write one, they must write project-specific DMPs for all of their research. A researcher who has written an umbrella DMP can still choose to write a project-specific DMP for particular research projects. This is recommended for externally funded research projects, for which only the standard Leiden DMP template is accepted.

2.3) Preserving the DMP

The archiving of the DMP is the responsibility of the data steward, not the researcher. The Faculty Protocol stipulates that DMPs are preserved centrally within the faculty or institute for a minimum retention period of 10 years. This should be the most up-to-date version that reflects the reality of the final research output, which the data steward will then archive.

The archived DMP will be accessible by the faculty data manager, faculty data stewards, faculty privacy officer and the (delegate of the) institute research director. Where the content of the DMP is deemed sensitive, access restrictions can be applied.

3) Publication Package Policy

Scope: The Publication Package Policy is **mandatory** for research that is published in a peer-reviewed journal.⁵

The 2022 DSW guidelines require the creation of publication packages: a compilation of all information needed to assess the results of a publication according to the principle of ‘retroactive accountability’ for verification purposes ([DSW, 2022](#)). While acknowledging the importance of accountability, the Institute of Political Science follows the precedent of the Faculty Protocol and is instead guided by **the transparent preservation of research underlying a publication**.

3.1) Elements of the publication package

The mandatory elements of a publication package, that all researchers must include, are:

- The publication or its persistent identifier (usually a DOI);
- The Data Management Plan (either a project-specific DMP or the personal umbrella DMP that applies);⁶
- Any quantitative research data relevant to the project:
 - This refers to processed (not raw) data, i.e. the data that is used to produce the analyses in the publication, including any code or scripts that produce this analysis.
 - Personal data should be de-identified (see [4.2](#)) unless the personal data is already (legally) publicly available.
 - If the data are already publicly available, they do not need to be included in the publication package, but a reference, link or persistent identifier of this material must be included in either the publication itself, or in the publication package.
 - In case preparing and publishing the processed data is not practically feasible given the amount of work required or the size of the processed data, an exception can be applied with the consent of the director of research.
- The available accompanying materials that are necessary to understand any qualitative and/or quantitative data underlying the publication:
 - This includes metadata that describes the research design and data, if this is not sufficiently elaborated on in the publication itself. What to be included here can be decided on in consultation with the data steward.
 - Examples of other accompanying materials include: codebooks, interview guides, questionnaires, surveys, blank consent forms, code/syntax, etcetera.

The optional elements of a publication package include:

- Any qualitative research data that is relevant to the project.

⁵ Article reviews and book reviews are not considered original research as defined by the Faculty Protocol, and therefore do not require a publication package.

⁶ For projects exempt from the DMP policy, but that fall under the publication package policy, a DMP does not need to be included in the package.

- Any *raw* research data relevant to the project, i.e. data in the form that it was first acquired for the project, and any computer code that is used to transform this into the processed research data.

3.2) Access conditions of the publication package

The institute recommends publication packages be shared under an open access license if there are no personal data or copyright restrictions. In the cases described below access may be restricted. In such cases only the researcher and data steward have access to the package, but there does need to be a mechanism for others to gain access to the restricted elements of the publication package (at least) if there is a legitimate interest from the perspective of scientific integrity.

Publication packages can be preserved under restricted access conditions if this is necessary because of the sensitivity of the data, and whether it can be anonymized or sufficiently de-identified. In exceptional cases, with highly sensitive data, even restricted access may not be appropriate. In such cases, the highly sensitive parts of the data can be excluded from the publication package, under the condition that this must be clearly motivated and the metadata that describes the data should be included in the publication package.

Elements of the publication package can also be restricted when copyrighted data is obtained from third parties for which the researcher has no permission to publish the (processed) data. As above, this data may need to have restricted access, or where not included at all an exception must be clearly motivated and the metadata included in the publication package should sufficiently describe how researchers can obtain the original data from the third party.

3.3) Responsibilities regarding Publication Packages

The corresponding author is responsible for assembling the publication package. If the corresponding author belongs to a different social science faculty in the Netherlands, they will be subject to their own Publication Package policy and will create the package accordingly. If the corresponding author is not required to submit a publication package, the (most senior) co-author from Leiden University is required to ensure that a publication package is assembled.

After the publication package is completed, it should be sent to the institute data steward for preservation. This submission should occur within one month of the publication going live. All publication packages are stored on DataverseNL, in the sub-Dataverse of the institute.⁷

3.4) Resources for completing the Publication Package

A detailed ‘how-to’ guide for compiling in the publication package can be found in [Appendix B](#). This explains the different elements of the package, and the necessary documents depending on the methodology used/data collected. Included in this is a description of metadata; this is the data that describes a researcher’s data.

⁷ If the necessary contents of the publication package are stored in another publicly accessible repository, it suffices to link to this in the DataverseNL publication package.

4) Privacy

Scope: All research projects involving the collection of personal data are subject to privacy considerations.

When research involves human participants or the collection of personal data, respect for participants' privacy is imperative, and stipulated by EU regulation (GDPR). GDPR applies when the personal data of EU/EEA citizens is processed, or personal data is processed within the EU/EEA.

Therefore, when conducting research involving human participants, or the collection of personal data, researchers must:

- Submit a research ethics review request before starting data collection, if required by the research funder. Information regarding under what circumstances ethics review is required, and how this process works, can be found on the [faculty website](#).
- Submit a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) to the [FSW Privacy Office](#), to assess whether research data management complies with GDPR.
- Create a data sharing agreement (DSA) if personal data will be shared with third parties (including researchers at other universities). This is signed between universities, not individual researchers. More information about this is available in the Faculty Protocol. Researchers are advised to contact the privacy officer who will draft this document and advise under which situations this agreement is necessary.

Personally identifiable data that is already publicly available,⁸ such as parliamentary speeches or published survey data, is not subject to ethics approval /a DPIA /a DSA.

More information on privacy can be found in the Faculty Protocol.

4.1) Personal data collection

In accordance with GDPR, personal data refers to any information pertaining to an individual through which they can be identified: a name, (email, IP) address, age. Within this is higher risk 'special category data', which involves ethnicity/race, religious/philosophical/political beliefs, health and medical data, sexual orientation or history. It is expected that researchers practice data minimization: only collecting the information needed, and de-identify this information as soon as possible.

To collect special category data, there must be robust legal grounds and additional risk-mitigating measures taken. Two of the frequently applicable legal grounds for collecting personal data are:

1. Informed consent: To be legitimate, consent must be given freely, must be unambiguous and informed, and there must be evidence that consent was given.⁹ For children under

⁸ This means it is licensed for reuse, and does not exist behind a paywall or other access barrier.

⁹ Evidence of consent includes a signed consent form, video/audio recording of consent being given, records of a researcher confirming consent was given, etcetera. For more information, please speak with the privacy officer.

13y/o parental consent must be gained, and for children under 16y/o co-consent from a parent must be gained.

2. **Public interest:** As an academic institution conducting scientific research, personal data can sometime be processed for research on the basis of public interest. From an ethical perspective and for special categories of personal data, consent is usually still required.

The faculty privacy officer should be consulted for advice regarding the legality of collecting personally identifiable data.

4.2) De-identifying personally identifiable data

Researchers should de-identify data as soon as possible. There are two methods for the de-identification of data. The first is **anonymization**, which involves the permanent deletion of all information that can be traced back to the participants. When data are anonymized, GDPR guidelines no longer apply, and data can be shared openly.

Under certain circumstances, anonymization can be difficult or impossible. Here, a second approach of **pseudonymization** can be used. This involves the replacement of personal information (such as names) to ensure privacy. A conversion key is then stored securely,¹⁰ so data can be traced back to the participant. As long as data is pseudonymized/a conversion key exists, the data is not anonymous and is subject to GDPR guidelines.

There are situations in which anonymization/pseudonymization is not necessary. For example, researchers collecting qualitative data can include in the informed consent that the personal data be used and retained. If retaining data is necessary for follow-up by the researcher, this should be made clear when obtaining consent.

As a general rule, de-identification is successful when identifying the persons behind the data would be disproportionately effortful for an average member of the public.

4.3) Storing personally identifiable data

When storing personally identifiable data, additional considerations are needed to ensure the data is as secure as possible. It is required that researchers:

- **DO NOT** use platforms that store data outside the EEA (e.g. google drive)
- **DO NOT** use personal accounts across services (e.g. on p:/drive, OneDrive, SURFdrive)
- **DO** use university storage where possible: J:/drive¹¹
- **DO** add additional layers of protection when necessary, such as encryption, password protection, etcetera.

¹⁰ The conversion key should ideally be destroyed once the research is complete, if possible. Before deletion, it must be stored on a secure server, and never preserved in a repository.

¹¹ While J:/drive is the primary recommendation, storage solutions are not limited to this platform. Research Drive and YODA are other recognized secure solutions.

- **DO** digitize non-digital data where feasible; where infeasible, non-digital personal data should be stored securely at Leiden University.

Before deciding on a storage solution, it is recommended to speak with the institute data steward or privacy officer to ensure that data is sufficiently protected.

5) Data Retention and Deletion Policy

Scope: All research projects are subject to the data retention and deletion policy.

Leiden University defines a minimum retention period of 10 years for all research data. After 10 years data can be deleted at the request of the researcher, or if required by external constraints (e.g. the consent of research participants). This applies to digital and non-digital data, and to all staff falling under [1.2](#).

For data deletion and retention, the institute follows the policy outlined in the Faculty Protocol. Please see this document for a step-by-step guide as to how data can be deleted, including the inclusion of such matters in the employee exit procedure.

6) Open Access Publishing

Scope: Leiden's 2017 [Open Access Policy](#) requires that all scholarly articles, book chapters in edited collections, and conference papers are made Open Access via the Leiden Repository.

[Open Access](#) publishing ensures that full texts are directly accessible online, with no permission or price restrictions. Publishing papers Open Access increases the visibility of research and thus its impact, making knowledge accessible to a much wider audience. It is required that Leiden researchers make their short-form publications open access, which can be done in two ways.

One path is publishing Open Access; selecting a journal that guarantees publication directly in Open Access. Most journals charge an Article Processing Charge (APC) or an Open Access fee to facilitate this service. In many cases there are agreements between the university of the corresponding author and the journal that cover these APCs. If there is no such agreement, the APC can be covered from a researchers' research grant (if budgeted) or other funds; the Institute of Political Science does not cover APCs. A list of Leiden University's open access costs can be found on the [journal browser](#).

A second path is making the publication Open Access based on [Article 25fa of the Dutch Copyright Act](#) (the so-called Taverne amendment), whereby short-form publications resulting from research funded in whole or in part by public funds can be made Open Access after an

embargo of six months, irrespective of the publisher's terms and conditions. This can be done by submitting the publishers PDF when registering the publication in LUCRIS.

WARNING: Predatory Journals: Predatory journals can take APC payments from researchers without publishing the article, or publish the article without an editorial or peer review process. To avoid choosing predatory journals, researchers can use [Think, Check, Submit](#) to identify trusted journals. In addition, researchers can contact the Centre for Digital Scholarship (CDS), which can help them choose trusted outlets.

7) General RDM Guidelines

Alongside the mandatory policy outlined in sections 2-6, the institute offers **guidance** for RDM best practices.

7.1) Before the research project

When within the scope of the aforementioned policies, write the DMP and set-up the publication package structure.

Preregistration of the project could also be considered: This is most applicable for quantitative projects or confirmatory research, when the aim is to replicate a study. With preregistration, a research plan is specified in advance and submitted in a register, which includes the hypotheses and methodology. Various platforms facilitate preregistration, including the [Open Science Framework \(OSF\)](#), and some academic journals allow for peer-reviewed preregistration.

7.2) During the research project

7.2.1) Storage of non-personal data

Researchers are strongly encouraged to store their research data on J:/drive, Research Drive or YODA where possible, and use university hardware (e.g. laptops, hard drives). Personal storage accounts should be avoided. When data must be physically stored, the Institute strongly recommends using hardware provided by Leiden University to store data (laptops, hard disks, phones, recorders, cameras, etcetera).

Projects generating large amounts of data may need additional storage capacity- please contact the data steward for advice regarding the most appropriate storage solutions.

7.2.2) Data documentation

Researchers are encouraged to ensure their data are sufficiently documented; this includes descriptions about the data themselves (metadata), but also descriptions of individual files, codebooks, etcetera. This can be done with a 'readme' document, which can be imbedded in the folder structure alongside the relevant data. Such a document would explain what the folder

contains, the author(s) of the content of the folder, and any information needed to understand the contents (e.g. file naming conventions, abbreviations, variable naming conventions, etcetera).

7.3) After the research project

7.3.1) Data Licensing

Through licensing their work, researchers delineate permissions for the ownership and reuse of their data. The most common licenses are Creative Commons, which offer varying degrees of reuse and redistribution of data depending on researcher preferences. However, the appropriate license ultimately depends on researcher preference, the sensitivity of the data, or funder/journal requirements. For more information, contact the Centre for Digital Scholarship to speak with their licensing experts.

7.3.2) LUCRIS

Researchers should register their publications on the Leiden University Current Research Information System. As well as scientific publications (books, chapters, articles), editorial positions and professional publications can be registered. This increases the visibility of publications, guarantees their preservation, and is an opportunity to showcase the research output of the institute.

Publications can be registered throughout the year, but an annual report is generated on 31st December that details the OA publications of that calendar year. To be included in this report, researchers must register their publications before this deadline. For detailed instructions on how to register a publication in LUCRIS, please see [the Library Website](#).

7.3.3) Data repositories

Publication packages are archived by the institute on DataverseNL. If the researcher wants to preserve the publication package in an additional location, the institute asks that the repository has a CoreTrustSeal certification, which ensures the security of the data deposited. Information about which repositories are CoreTrustSeal certified can be found [here](#). The chosen repository should ideally also offer clear access conditions, as well as standardized exchange protocols so that metadata are both publicly accessible and machine actionable.

Sensitive data may need to be stored with restricted access conditions, and need to meet additional legal requirements under GDPR: This includes that it is stored within the EU. To ensure that a repository meets GDPR requirements, contact the Privacy Officer.

Appendix

Appendix A) Staff and Responsibilities:

Institute Data Steward: DataStewardPoWe@fsw.leidenuniv.nl

For all questions pertaining to research data management; including, but not limited to, DMPs, publication packages, open access publishing, data preservation, etcetera.

Privacy Officer: privacy@fsw.leidenuniv.nl

For questions including, but not limited to, privacy, data protection, DSAs, DPIAs, GDPR.

Ethics Committee: ethiekmaatschappijwetenschappen@fsw.leidenuniv.nl

For ethical approval for a research project, or queries pertaining to research ethics.

Research Data Manager: datamanagement@fsw.leidenuniv.nl

For questions including, but not limited to, (RDM) policy, pre-registration, data storage.

Centre for Digital Scholarship: cds@library.leidenuniv.nl

For questions including, but not limited to, copyright, data licensing, research software and data engineering.

Appendix B) RDM Resources

B.1) Personal Umbrella DMP template

Personal Umbrella DMP template: [Click here](#)

Personal Umbrella DMP template 'how-to' guide: [Click here](#)

B.2) Publication Package 'how-to' guide

Publication Package 'how-to' guide: [Click here](#)